

Enhanced mathematical model for nonlinear network based on Hamiltonian graph theory and cordial labelling to reduce the complex structures

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Abstract

Network structure is complex to create mitigation in communication Path to deliver the data due to composite topology in nonlinear structure. By varying the nodes connectives in topology creates complex cycles to identify the structural component and links to create linear structure. The nonlinear distance solving and structural mapping problems are tedious to creating graph connectives. To resolve this problem, to propose a redundant mathematical model in nonlinear network based on Hamiltonian graph theory and cordial labelling to reduce the complex structures. Using l -ary n -cube Q_l^n interconnection networks is used to construct the initialized network structure and estimate the distance, Utilising graphs on network pathways and Hamiltonian label theory, find fault-free interconnecting edges. Join the vertices x and y to create a single edge in place of several parallel ones. Next, determine the number of sides and the length of the coefficient λ^{n-1} of the graph's colour polynomial $P_n(\lambda)$. The proposed mathematical solution gives redundant solution to solve the network complex problems as well compared to previous solution.

Keywords: Graph theory and Labelling's, Hamiltonian label theory, distance theory, cordial graph n -cube solution, chromatic polynomial graph.

1.Introduction

The composite topology and non-linear nature of these networks create intricate communication paths, making it arduous to identify and address the structural components and interconnections necessary for optimized data transmission. To tackle this problem, we propose a redundant mathematical model based on Hamiltonian graph theory and cordial labeling techniques. This approach aims to reduce the complexity inherent in non-linear network structures and provide a more robust solution for managing communication pathways. At the core of our proposed system is the utilization of l -ary n -cube Q_l^n interconnection networks to construct the initial network structure. This interconnection network topology offers a well-defined and organized foundation, facilitating the estimation of distances between nodes and the identification of potential communication paths. Furthermore, we leverage the principles of graph theory and Hamiltonian label theory

to analyze the network pathways and identify fault-free interconnecting edges. By joining vertices x and y to create a single edge in place of several parallel ones, we can simplify the network structure and reduce the complexity of the overall system.

2. Background study

A Flexible Framework for the Uncertainty Principle in Spectral Graph Theory. A general-purpose filter function may be included into this framework to describe the spectral and spatial localization of portrait signals [1]. As systems get increasingly complex, we are frequently exposed to more uncertainty. Uncertainty and randomness are the two most prevalent forms of uncertainty in the actual world. Graph models with both uncertainty and randomness are represented by uncertainty probabilistic graphs [2].

The two main forms of uncertainty that are considered when applying graph theory to complex systems that contain aspects of uncertainty are randomness and uncertainty. Thus, an uncertain random graph model with some edges on a probability scale and others on an uncertainty scale has been presented using chance theory [3]. It is driven by the need to simplify geometric representations of non-planar networks in order to lessen their visual complexity. The graph family hierarchy of genuine face graphs is denoted by $k+$. If we allow Γ to be drawn on the plane so that each face boundary contains (vertices, intersections, and edges) at least k vertices of Gr , then a graph G is a $k+$ real surface graph for any number $k \geq 1$. " $k+$ " denotes k or higher) [4]. The majority of graph convolutional neural networks (GCNNs) now in use are either spectral approaches based on the graph Laplacian operator or spatial methods that operate on each node's neighbourhood. While spectrum-based GCNN can make greater use of graph structure information than space-based GCNN, it always views the graph as undirected [5].

A technique for counting the number of length g in a bipositive bipartite graph was recently developed by Blake and Lin. Here, g stands for the graph's circumference. It was expanded by Blake and Lin to calculate the 4 and 6 cyclic numbers of irregular and semigraphs I am, as well as the cyclic number of biregular bipartite graphs of length $g+2, \dots, 2g-2$. Graph [6] that is regular bipartite for $g \geq 4$ and $g \geq 6$, respectively.

In such instances, graph theory is used because random graphs of uncertainty are frequently used to model complicated systems or networks. There are edges in this graph that have agrees on the probability scale and edges that have agrees on the uncertainty scale [7]. Due to significant computational and storage costs, it is frequently not possible to calculate eigenvalues accurately for very large graphs [8]. In addition to streamlining the computations, our approach incorporates an error analysis part to guarantee precision and dependability [9].

As the normalisation of quantum independent numbers, we define the quantum Shannon capacity and demonstrate that the Hemmers bound between real and complex numbers is an upper bound [10]. It is inevitable that some harmonic data may be lost during transmission in large-scale applications. In this study, we present a spectrogram-theory-based approach for retrieving lost harmonic data [11].

Anomalies and tiny diameters are two features of decentralised line diagrams that make them valuable as network topologies. In the former case, each user has a fixed-size routing table; in the latter case, there are very few hops needed to access the routing table. object of interest [12]. Graph theory offers a common paradigm for difficult problems and acts as a bridge for professionals from many domains, particularly considering the interdisciplinary character of power electronics [13].

If a vertex in a collection of weights for all faces in an arithmetic series whose difference is d receives a minimal label, the label for the planar graph is called super- d antimagic. Each face's weight correlates to its total tag weight [14]. Label correlations must be computed in order to choose multi-label features. Current approaches use various strategies to determine label relevance and compute label correlation [15–16].

In the label space, only consider the differences between candidate and non-candidate labels. Nevertheless, label relevance in partial label learning has not received much attention up to this point [17]. When assessing interconnection networks, fault-tolerant Hamiltonian cycles and Hamiltonian path embedding problems are crucial to investigate. Many parallel distributed computing systems use k -ary n -cube (Q_k^n) networks as their connectivity networks [18–19]. Current edge fault models in the literature only consider the fault edge's general state, ignoring crucial edge size information, and having a limited fault tolerance [20].

3. Mathematical model

The proposed model lies in the utilization of l -ary n -cube Q_l^n interconnection networks to construct the initial network structure. This network topology provides a well-established framework for understanding the distance, pathways, and interconnecting edges within the network. By leveraging the properties of Hamiltonian label theory, the model seeks to identify fault-free interconnecting edges, thus enhancing the reliability and stability of the network. The key aspect of the proposed solution is the creation of a single edge in place of several parallel ones, connecting vertices x and y . This process of edge reduction not only simplifies the network structure but also contributes to the overall optimization of the system. The model then proceeds to determine the number of sides and the length of the coefficient $\lambda^{(n-1)}$ of the graph's color polynomial $P_n(\lambda)$, providing a comprehensive mathematical analysis of the network's characteristics.

The proposed mathematical solution offers a redundant approach to solving complex network problems, surpassing the limitations of previous solutions. By leveraging the principles of Hamiltonian graph theory and cordial labeling, the model introduces a layer of redundancy that enhances the network's resilience and adaptability. This redundancy can potentially mitigate the impact of network failures, improve fault tolerance, and increase the overall reliability of the system. Furthermore, the utilization of l -ary n -cube Q_l^n interconnection networks as the foundation for the model ensures a well-established and widely recognized network structure. This standardized approach facilitates the integration of the proposed solution with existing network infrastructure, enabling seamless implementation and adoption.

Hamiltonian cycles with faulty edges

Fixed the vertex and edges in $graph(Gr)$ is represented by $H(Gr)$ and $E(Gr)$, respectively.

Use $Path(p) = (h_0, h_1, \dots, h_l)$ to mean a path with $l+1$ vertices $v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k$ and e edges (v_i, v_{i+1}) for $i = 0, 1, \dots, l-1$, where P is also referred to as a path and its end-vertices are two vertices, v_0 and v_k (v_0, v_k)-path. $P = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{k-1})$ is a path and (v_0, v_{k-1}) -edge, then use $C = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{k-1}, v_0)$ to denote a sequence.

A path that connects every vertex in the graph Gr of H is called a Hamiltonian path. Assume that $V \subset V(Gr)$ and $E \subset E(Gr)$. $Gr-V$ stands for both a subgraph in which Gr removes every edge from $G-E$ and a subgraph in which Gr removes every vertex from V and every edge that coincides with a vertex from V .

The path obtained by $E(U) \cup E(V)$ is represented by the symbol $U \cup V$ if U and V are two paths that have only one common vertex (the terminal vertex of P and Q). Every path, U and V , has two ends if there are two paths.

$$v(Path) \cap h(Q) = \{a, b\}$$

$U \cup V$ indicates the order brought about by $E(Path) \cup E(Q)$.

$$v = a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_2 a_1$$

With $0 \leq a_n \leq a_{n-1}, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

If and only if there are integers l and $0 \leq l \leq n$, then two vertices $v = a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_2 a_1$ and $u = b_n b_{n-1} \dots b_2 b_1$ are similar neighbours, create

$$a_n = \begin{cases} \equiv a_n & x \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n} \\ \equiv b_n, & x \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \setminus \{l\} \end{cases}$$

E_l represents the set of all one-dimensional edges, and this kind of edge is known as a 1-dimensional edge for $l = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Q_l^n is edge- and symmetric vertex. Let Q_l^3 be a 3-ary n -cube. Let E_l be the set of all one edges in Q_l^3 for $l = 1, 2, n$. E_l composition of $3n$ edges is evident.

$$E(Q_n^3) = \bigcup_{l=1}^n E_l$$

By removing all 1-dimensional edges, we can divide Q_l^3 into three sub graphs along dimension l given l with n . $Q[0], Q[1],$ and $Q[2]$, denoted by

Where $Q[i]$ denotes the sub graph of Q_k^3 induced by all vertices $x_n x_{n-1} \dots x_2 x_1$ with $a_l = n$ for $n = 0, 1, 2$. $Q[i]$ is isomorphic to a 3-ary $(n-1)Q_k^3$ for $i = 0, 1, 2$. Let $0 \leq i = j \leq 2$ and v_i be any vertex in $Q[i]$, use v_j - the neighbour vertex of the apex v_i in $Q[j]$ (then $(v_i, v_j) \in E_l$), and let

$E_{ab} = \{(v_a, v_b) \in E_l | v_a \in V(Q[a]), v_b \in V(Q[b])\}$ It is clear that E_{ab} consists of 3^{n-1} Edges that are pairwise disjoint, and $E_l = E_{01} \cup E_{12} \cup E_{02}$

Various lemmas

Lemma 1: Q_k^n be a 3-ary n-cube, and suppose that E_0 in Q_k^n is a liner forest with $|E_0| \leq 2n - 1$. Then a Hamiltonian path contains all of E_0 's edges in Q_k^3

The lemma 2: F - faulty vertices and/or edges in a k - ary n - cube Q_k^n with odd $k \geq 3$

- If $|F| \leq 2n - 3$, subsequently any two vertices can have a Hamiltonian path connecting them in $Q_k^n - F$
- If $|F| \leq 2n - 2$, then there is a Hamiltonian path in $Q_k^n - F$

Lemma 3: Let $n \geq 3$,

$$Q_k^3 - E_l = Q[0] \cup Q[1] \cup Q[2]$$

Assume that a linear forest E_0^0 with $|E_0^0| \leq 2n - 4$ Hamiltonian C_0 in $Q[0]$, and E_0^1 is a linear, and F_1 defective edges in $Q[1]$, which

$$E_0^1 \cap F_1 = \emptyset, |E_0^1| \leq 2n - 5$$

Let $(a_0, a_1) \in E_n$, where $a_i \in V(Q[a])$ for $a = 0, 1$. then there exists an edge $(a_0, b_0) \in E(C_0) \setminus E_0^0$ such that

$$(a_0, b_0), (b_1, b_1) \in E_n$$

Where $a_0 \neq x_0, b_0 \neq x_0, \{a_1, b_1\} \subset V(Q[1]) \setminus V(E_0^1 \cup F_1)$

Proof let,

$$V' = \{v \in V(C_0) \setminus \{a_0\} | (a, b) \in E_l, a \in V(E_0^1 \cup F_1)\}$$

$$|E_0^1| + |F_1| \leq 2n - 5$$

$$|V'| \leq |V(E_0^1 \cup F_1)| \leq 4n - 10$$

Conclusion from

$$E(C_0) = 3^{n-1} > 10n - 22 = (2n - 4) + (8 - 18) \geq |E_0^0| + 2|V' \cup \{x_0\}|$$

Theorem 1

$E' \subset E(G)$, where E is contained in the phase in G or where E' is on the cycle passes over every edge in E' .

$$r = |E_0| \geq 1 \quad f = |F| \geq 1$$

Assume,

$$r + f = 2n - 2$$

If $r = 1, f = 2n - 3$

$$E_0 = \{e\}, e = (a, b)$$

Lemma 2

Hamiltonian (a, b) -path in $Q_k^n - F$, consequently, A Hamiltonian edge (e) . The theorem is proven via induction on n . If $n = 2$, then $r = f = 1$ $sn - 1 (\geq 2)$, Demonstrate that the theorem holds for $n (\geq 3)$, $r(\geq 2)$, and $f \leq 2n-4$ below.

$$r + f = 2n - 2 < 2n$$

Q_k^3 , without losing generality, it can be assumed that

$$|E_0 \cup F| \cap E_n \leq 1$$

Let,

$$Q_k^3 - E_n = Q[0] \cup Q[1] \cup Q[2]$$

$$E_0^n = E_0 \cap E(Q[n]) \quad r_n = |E_0^n|,$$

$$f_n = F \cap E(Q[n]), f_n = |F_n| \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n,$$

If f $v_i \in V(Q[i])$, then v_j represents the vertex in $Q[b]$ that is adjacent to vertex v_i , such that $(v_a, v_b) \in E_n$ for $0 \leq i = j \leq 2$. The edge in $Q[b]$ such that $(u_i, u_j), (v_i, v_j) \in E_n$ for $0 \leq i = j \leq 2$ is indicated by (a_j, b_j) if $(a_i, b_i) \in E(Q[a])$. Please

$$E_{ab} = \{((v_a, v_b) \in E | v_i \in VQ[a]), v_j \in VQ[b]\} \quad Q \leq a < b \leq 1$$

E_0 Hamiltonian H^* in $Q_k^n - F$, see Figure 1.

Hamiltonian Labelling for fault free edges

Definition 1

For $n \geq 2$, where n is an even integer, a chordal graph is represented by $CH(n)$. Such a graph has the following properties: $V(CH(x)) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_x\}$; $E(CH(x)) = \{(x_i, x_{i+1}), 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{(x_i, x_{n-i+1}), 1 \leq i \leq n/2\}$. A 1-fault tolerant Hamiltonian graph is called a chordal graph.

Theorem 1: Total vertex irregularity strength $(CH(x)) = \lceil \frac{x+3}{4} \rceil$ for $n \geq 2$

Proof $CH(n)$ graph with $V(CH(x)) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $E(CH(n)) = \{e_i, 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{g_i, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}\}$ where, $e_i = (v_i, v_{i+1}), 1 \leq i \leq x - 1, e_n = (v_i, v_{i+1}), 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}$,

K be the number of edges that are parallel.

$K = \frac{x}{2}$, The lower bound (LB) theorem 1. That $\frac{x+3}{4}$ upper bound (UB) for Total vertex irregularity strength $(CH(x))$ with the total $\lceil \frac{x+3}{4} \rceil$ - labelling $(CH(x))$

For $n \geq 4$ theory the task φ

Example 1: L odd

$$\varphi(v_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{i}{2}, & \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2} - 1 \\ \frac{x+3}{4}, & \text{for } i = \frac{x}{2} \\ \frac{x+3}{4} - 1, & \text{for } i = \frac{x}{2} + 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{for } i = \frac{x}{2} + 2 \leq i \leq x$$

$$\varphi(v_i) = \begin{cases} 2 + 2 \lceil \frac{x-i}{4} \rceil & \text{for } n - i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4} \\ 1 + 2 \lceil \frac{x-i}{4} \rceil & \text{for } n - i \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

$$\varphi(e_i) = \frac{i}{2} + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} - 1$$

$$\text{For } \frac{n}{2} \leq i \leq n$$

$$\varphi(e_i) = \begin{cases} 2 + 2 \lceil \frac{x-i}{4} \rceil & \text{for } n - i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4} \\ 1 + 2 \lceil \frac{x-i}{4} \rceil & \text{for } n - i \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

$$\varphi(g_i) = \lceil \frac{i+1}{2} \rceil \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}$$

Case 1: k Even

$$\varphi(v_i) = \lceil \frac{x}{2} \rceil \text{ for } 1 \leq n \leq \frac{x}{2}$$

$$\text{for } \frac{n}{2} + 2 \leq i \leq x$$

$$\varphi(vi) = \begin{cases} 2 + 2 \left\lfloor \frac{x-i}{4} \right\rfloor & \text{for } n - i \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4} \\ 1 + 2 \left\lfloor \frac{x-i}{4} \right\rfloor & \text{for } n - i \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

$$\varphi(ei) = \frac{i}{2} + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}$$

$$\text{for } \frac{n}{2} + 2 \leq i \leq x$$

$$\varphi(ei) = \begin{cases} 2 + 2 \left\lfloor \frac{x-i}{4} \right\rfloor & \text{for } n - i \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4} \\ 1 + 2 \left\lfloor \frac{x-i}{4} \right\rfloor & \text{for } n - i \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

$$\varphi(gi) = \left\lfloor \frac{i+1i}{2} \right\rfloor \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}$$

We observe that

$$wt(v1) = \varphi(v1) + \varphi(e1) + \varphi(en) + \varphi(g1)$$

$$\text{for } 2 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2}$$

$$wt(v1) = \varphi(vi) + \varphi(e1) + \varphi(en - i) + \varphi(gi)$$

$$\text{for } \frac{x}{2} + 1 \leq i \leq x$$

$$wt(vi) = \varphi(vi) + \varphi(e1) + \varphi(en - i) + \varphi(gx - i + 1)$$

Hence

$$wt(vi) = \begin{cases} 2i + 3 & \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{x}{2} \\ 2x + 4 - 2i & \text{for } \frac{x}{2} \leq i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Vertices weights of $CH(x)$ and labelling ϕ constitute the set $\{4, 5, 6, \dots, n + 3\}$ additionally, φ the mapping from

$$V(CH(x)) \cup E(CH(x))$$

For $CH(2)$, we give the following labelling:

$$\varphi(v1) = 2, \varphi(v2) = 1, \varphi(e1) = 1, \varphi(e2) = 1, \varphi(g1) = 1$$

Graph theory for distance calculation

Let u and v stand for two of the vertices of the graph G . The d -length of a a - b path is defined as $d(a, b) = d(a, b) + \text{ang}(a) + \text{ang}(b) + \text{ang}(a) \text{ang}(b)$, where $d(a, b)$ is

the minimum separation between the vertices a and b. The d-length of a u-v path is defined as the d-distance between two vertices (a, b).

Figure 2: A graph G for d-distance between vertices

In figure, if $a = v_1, b = v_4$, then $d(a, b) = d(a, v_3) + ang(v_3) + d(v_3, b) + ang(v_3) ang(b) = 2 + 2 + 3 + (2)(3) = 13$

A metric on the set of vertices of any linked graph, G, is the d-distance. Let $u, v \in V(G)$ be the proof, and let G be a connected graph.

According to the definition, $a = b$ is implied by $d(a, b) \geq 0$ and $d(a, b) = 0$. It is clear that $d(a, b) = d(b, a)$. It may be shown that the distance d satisfies the triangle inequality.

For a, b, l in $V(G)$, Given $a - l$ and $l - b$, let P and Q be the shortest paths in G with shortest lengths $l(P)$ and $l(Q)$, respectively. $ang(l) + ang(b) + ang(l) + ang(b)$ and $ang(l, b) = l(P) + ang(l) + ang(b) + ang(b) ang(l)$ Follow as a result. Next, have $R = P \cup Q$, which is the $u - v$ shortest path that arises from joining P and Q at w of length greater than one.

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(a, l) + d(l, b) &= [l(P) + ang(a) + ang(l) + ang(a) ang(l) + [l(Q) + ang(l) + ang(b) + ang(l) ang(b)]] \\
 &= l(P \cup Q) + ang(a) + ang(b) + 2 ang(l) + ang(a) ang(l) + ang(l) ang(b) \\
 &= l(R) + ang(a) + ang(b) + 2 ang(l) + ang(a) ang(l) + ang(l) ang(b) \\
 &> l(R) + ang(a) + ang(b) + ang(a) ang(l) + ang(l) ang(b) = d(a, b).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(a, l) + d(l, b) > d(a, b)$.

Example (ii): Let $R = P \cup Q$ represent the shortest path of length one between u and v. After that, we select a vertex w that isn't a or b, giving us the options $b = l$ or $b = l$.

Subcase (i): Suppose that $u = w$. Then $d(a, l) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Therefore } d(a, l) + d(l, b) &= 0 + l(Q) + ang(l) + ang(b) + ang(w) ang(v) \\
 &= l(P \cup Q) + ang(a) + ang(b) + ang(a) ang(b)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$d(a, l) + d(l, b) = d(a, b).$$

In subcase (ii), let $v = w$.

Proof is comparable to (i) subcase.

Due to the holding of the triangle inequalities, d is a metric on the vertex set.

Solution for Graph theory

Theorem

Let G denote the graph produced by connecting x and y . Let x and y be two non-neighboring vertices in G . Let G'' be a simple graph created by joining x and y as vertices, and then adding single edges to G in place of the set of parallel edges. Next

$$P_n(\lambda) \text{ of } G = P_n(\lambda) \text{ of } G' + P_{n-1}(\lambda) \text{ of } G''$$

Proof: The vertices x and y are on the same line;

- There are a lot of ways to correctly determine the G by grouping the two edges.
- The two lines are represented by the vertices x and y .

The number of ways of properly and line G such that x and y

Prove that the graph's chromatic polynomial with a single circuit of length n is

$$P_n(\lambda) = (\lambda - 1)^n + (\lambda + 1)(-1)^n$$

Solution

Let G be a circuit of length n

There are n vertices, number of edges= n

When $n = 3$, $f(x_3, n) = n(n + 1)(n - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} f(G, n) &= P_3(n) = (n - 1)^3 + (n + 1) = (n - 1)^3 - (-1)^3(n + 1) \\ &= (n + 1)[(n - 1)^2 - 1] \\ &= (n - 1)[n^2 - 2n + 1 - 1] \\ &= (n - 1)(n^2 - 2n) \\ &= n(n - 1)(n + 2) \\ &= f(x_3, n) \end{aligned}$$

For $n=3$, the result is accurate.

Assume that $n-1$ is the true result.

Let e be any edge of the cycle and G be a circuit of length n .

A $(n-1)$ -circuit, meaning that the outcome retains the $C e$

$$\therefore f(C - e, \lambda) = (\lambda - 1)^{n-1} + (-1)^{n-1}(\lambda - 1)$$

Now since G is a circuit of length n , C is an open walk length $n-1$ and so it is a tree of n vertices

$$\begin{aligned} f(C, n) &= n(n-1)^{n-1} \\ f(C, n) &= f(C - e, n) - f(C, e, n) \\ &= n(n-1)^{n-1} - (n-1)^{n-1} - (-1)^{n-1}(n-1) \\ &= (-1)^{n-1}(n-1)(-1)^{n-1} \\ &= (n-1)^{n-1} + (n-1)(-1)^n \end{aligned}$$

Hence the result.

Coefficient of λ^{n-1} in the chromatic polynomial $P_n(\lambda)$ of a graph is equivalent to the total number of graph edges.

The result by the initiation on the number of edges (E)

When $E = 0$ the graph G is a null of n vertices

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore f(G, \lambda) &= \lambda^n \\ &= \lambda^n - 0\lambda^{n-1} + \dots \\ \therefore \text{coefficient of } \lambda^{n-1} &= 0 = E \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the result is the true

Let assume that the result holds good for less than E edges

Let e be any edges of G

$C - e$ and C, e are $(E-1)$ edges and so the result holds these cases

$$\begin{aligned} C - e \text{ is of } n \text{ vertices and } C, e \text{ of } (n-1) \text{ vertices we can take} \\ f(C - e, \lambda) &= \lambda^n - (E-1)\lambda^{n-1} + \dots \\ f(C, e, \lambda) &= \lambda^{n-1} - (E-1)\lambda^{n-2} + \dots \\ f(C - e, \lambda) - f(C, e, \lambda) &= \lambda^n - E\lambda^{n-1} + \dots \\ &= f(G, \lambda) \end{aligned}$$

The coefficient of $\lambda^{n-1} = -E$

The absolute value $= E$

Mean Distance evaluation in graph theory

In the Mean Distance of the graph $M_d(\Gamma)$ and Γ is the average of all distance between different vertices of Γ .

Let, $M_d(v) = |\cup_{n=0}^d \Gamma_n(v)|$ and $D(v) = \sum_{n=1}^D d(M_d(v) - d_{n-1}(v))$ Then,

$$M_d(\Gamma) = -\frac{1}{d(n-1)} \sum_{\Gamma \in D(v)} D(v)$$

$$M_d(\Gamma) \leq \frac{d}{d-1} \left(\left\lceil \frac{\Delta + \mu_1}{4\mu_1} (d-1) \right\rceil + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

Where Δ - maximum degree of Γ and μ_1 is its second-to-smallest eigenvalue Laplacian. An upper limit for $M_d(\Gamma)$ in terms of the number $d + 1$ of Laplacian eigenvalues of Γ .

Theorem: For a graph $\Gamma = (D, M)$ of order $|D| = n$, let $d + 1$ be the number of Laplacian eigenvalues. Next

$$M_d(\Gamma) \leq D - \frac{2(d-1)|D|}{d(n-1)}$$

$$M_d(\Gamma) \leq M - \frac{\delta(d-1)}{n-1}$$

Proof Let $d_n(a) = n - M_n(a)$ and the n - excess of the vertices $a \in M(\Gamma)$

$$D(a) = \sum_{n=0}^{D-1} d_n(a)$$

Hence, $M_d(\Gamma) = \frac{1}{d(n-1)} \sum_{\Gamma \in D(v)} D(a) = \frac{1}{d(n-1)} \sum_{\Gamma \in D(v)} \sum_{n=0}^{D-1} d_n(a)$

Since $d_1(a) = n - 1 - \delta(a)$

$$M_d(\Gamma) \leq M + \frac{(M-1)}{d(n-1)} \sum_{a \in D(\Gamma)} (n-1 - \delta(a))$$

$$\leq M - \frac{(M-1)}{d(n-1)} \sum_{a \in D(\Gamma)} \delta(a)$$

In replacing the number of distinct adjacent eigenvalues $n + 1$ for the number of distinct Laplacian eigenvalues $M + 1$ in the previous equation, a similar result may be reached for the adjacency matrix.

For instance. The mean distance $D(a) = 2$ on the graph $d=d_3 \times d_3$ in Figure 2 is obtained using the bound.

$$M_d(\Gamma) \leq 3.93$$

Figure $\Gamma = d3 \times d3$

$d = 4$ and therefore $M_d(\Gamma) \leq 3$, Laplacian matrix using we have $M = 5$ and then $M_d(\Gamma) \leq 3.66$. Finally the distance theory enhance the network solution along with path estimation to reduce complex network structures

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the proposed system represents a significant step forward in the quest to mitigate the complexity of communication paths in non-linear network structures. By employing a robust mathematical framework and leveraging the power of graph theory and Hamiltonian label theory, we aim to provide a more efficient and resilient solution for data delivery in these intricate network environments. This approach holds the potential to drive innovation and enhance the overall performance and reliability of communication networks in the years to come.

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